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Parental Involvement, Religiosity And Internet Addiction As Correlates Of Risky Sexual Behaviour Among Out- Of School Adolescents In Mushin, Lagos State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the predictive influence of parental involvement, religiosity and internet addiction on risky sexual behaviour among out of school adolescents in Mushin, Lagos state. The descriptive research design of ex-post-facto type was used in the study. A multistage sampling technique was adopted to draw a sample size of two hundred and seventy two (272) out-of school adolescents from twelve different areas of Mushin, Lagos state. The participants responded to relevant adopted standardized instruments and the data obtained was analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and Multiple Regression statistical tools. The results showed that sexual risky behaviour is significantly correlated with internet addiction ($r = .794$; $p < .05$); religiosity ($r = .783$; $p < .05$) and parental involvement ($r = .754$; $p < .05$). Also, the following beta weights represent the predictive strength of the independent variables observed in accordance from the most effective to the least; internet addiction ($\beta = .204$, $t = 2.889$, $P < 0.05$), religiosity ($\beta = .229$, $t = 2.416$, $P < 0.05$) and parental involvement ($\beta = .211$, $t = 2.160$, $P < 0.05$). It implies that while internet addiction is the most potent factor in predicting sexual risky behaviour among out of school adolescents, parental involvement was the least. Based on the above results, recommendations and suggestions were made to the various stakeholders.

Keywords: Internet addiction, parental involvement, religiosity, risky sexual behaviour

INTRODUCTION

Adolescents otherwise known as young people are important segment of Nigerian society. It makes up over a third (31.6 percent) of Nigeria's large and growing population (National Population Commission, 2013). Adolescents are generally defined as meaningful, young persons under various laws, conventions and culture, who are within the ages of 10-19 and 10- 24 years old according to World Health Organization (WHO, 2001). It is a period of life from puberty to attainment of full maturity (adulthood) or growth, a time of being young when one's appearance is full of freshness, vitality, vigour and young spirit. Adolescents also share certain characteristics that distinguish them from other generation. Such characteristic include, desire for independence, zealously, radicalism, rebellions, curiosity, sexual risk behaviours, etc. It is both a period of opportunity as well as a time of vulnerability- a time of experimentation with new ideas and options and marked with vulnerability to health risk and those related to unsafe reproductive health outcomes.

Until recently, adolescents in Nigeria were seen as a healthy segment of the population and received low priority for services. But biology and society bring on additional health challenges to them; those resulting from unprotected sex, violence and substance abuse. Ahonsi (2013) posited that adolescents in Nigeria have high burden of reproductive health problems. This assertion supported earlier surveys conducted on sexual behaviours of Nigerian Adolescents (National Demographic Health Survey,

2008; National HIV/AIDS and Reproductive Health Survey 2007; Integrated Biological and Behavioural Surveillance Survey, 2010) which show that Nigerian adolescent (15-19) almost half of the females (46.2%) and about a quarter of males (22.1%) have engaged in sexual intercourse. Worrying still is the data from the Federal Ministry of Education (2009) which found that 21% of upper primary school children surveyed indicated they have been involved in sexual intercourse yet only 40.6% who had two or more sexual partners in the past 12 months reported using a condom during their last sexual intercourse (National Demographic health Survey, 2008). Young people are clearly disproportionately affected by the epidemic in absolute terms even with the decline in overall HIV prevalence from 5.8% in 2001 to about 3.4% in 2012.

Adeyemo and Agokei (2008) opined that female adolescents often consider risky sexual behaviours as an elevation of status rather than being vicious. These patterns broadly conform to data from across Africa which suggests that the combination of being young, poor, female and lacking access to sexual health information and services carry particularly high risks for sexual reproductive health challenges (Coutinho, 2004). Ajuwon (2007) cited in Ahonsi (2013) was of the opinion that the fundamental bases of reproductive ill health among female is embedded in discriminatory social structures and stereotypes. For example, there is high tolerance for non-consensual sex (including rape) with girls by older men in communities, educational institutions, and work settings. It is against this backdrop that this research examined the extent to which parental involvement, internet addiction and religiosity predict risky sexual behaviour among out- of school adolescents in Mushin, Lagos State, Nigeria.

The first variable in this study is parental involvement. A multitude of definitions regarding parental involvement have been identified through previous research with definitions ranging from specific behaviours to broad overarching themes (Fan and Chen, 2001). Parental involvement is a multidimensional concept that includes behaviours relating to parental practice, parental behaviours, and parental communication (Fan and Chen, 2001). Regardless of the specific definition, a majority of research has indicated that limited parental involvement is associated with higher rates of engagement in sexual behaviours during adolescence (Ramirez-Valles, Zimmerman, and Juarez, 2002). Likewise, a high level of parental involvement is associated with lower levels of risky sexual behaviours during adolescence (Regnerus, 2006). When daughters experience a close relationship with their mother and report her as being highly involved in their lives, sexual debut is delayed (Miller, Norton, Curtis, Hill, Schvaneveldt, and Young, 1997). Additionally, young men who spend time with their fathers have shown a delay in sexual debut (Ramirez-Valles et al, 2002). Mothers have also indicated they talk more frequently with their adolescents regarding sexual behaviours compared to fathers (Whitaker, Miller, May, and Levin, 1999). Family communication regarding sex influences sexual decisions making among offspring (Karofsky, Zeng, and Kosorok, 2001) and reduces risky sexual behaviours among already sexually active teens (Booth-Butterfield and Sidelinger, 1998). Parents play an extremely important role in reducing both the physical and emotional risks associated with dangerous behaviour. (Odedokun,.(2020), Odedokun and Muraina, 2019)..

Parents, unlike a majority of educators, peers, or others, have a strong emotional bond to the children and can draw on this relationship to educate their wards regarding the risks of sexual behaviour. When parents create time and conducive environment for their wards, it fosters and promotes bonding, they will be able to discuss many issues that borders on their emotional and psychological wellbeing including their sexuality, dangers in premarital sexual exploration, unprotected sexual practices and so on. And this will help the young adolescents to see their parents as a role model and friends that value their existence and this could lead to a good behaviour that could reduce sexual risky behaviour. But in a case where there is no bonding or good relationship and communication between the young adolescents and their parents, they would relate with whosoever is there for them and if peradventure they have relationship with other sexual risk taker, it could promote high sexual risk behaviour among the out of school adolescents. This study therefore sought to investigate the influence of parental involvement on risky sexual behaviour among out -of school adolescents in Mushin, Lagos State, Nigeria

Another variable in this study is religiosity. It is a system of beliefs and practices by which groups of people interpret and respond to what they feel is supernatural and sacred (Johnstone, 1975). On the other hand religiosity is generally defined as the degree to which one believes in and is involved in religion. It is also related to the degree of religious commitment. Johnson, Jang, Larson, and De Li (2001) described religiosity as “the extent to which an individual is committed to the religion he or

she professes and its teachings, such as the individual's attitudes and behaviours reflect this commitment". It would be possible to say then that religiosity is capable of influencing an individual cognitively and behaviourally. According to Mokhlis (2006), religious persons have value systems that differ from those of the less religious and the non-religious. "A highly religious person will evaluate the world through religious schemas and thus will integrate his or her religion into much of his or her life" (Worthington et al., 2003). Mokhlis (2006) cites prior studies as evidence for the influence of religious beliefs on behaviour in areas such as parental attachment, clothing styles, eating and drinking, the use of cosmetics, social and political views and sexual behaviour. Clearly, motives for participating in religious experiences are linked to religion.

Since religiosity is affecting the individual's behaviour then it would be possible to hypothesize that the religious commitment may also be extended beyond religion itself and those people with high religiosity would be expected to exhibit a similar commitment in other aspects of their life, such as commitment to family relations and social and cultural norms. For example, according to Welch, Title, and Petee (1991), research has shown that religiosity is a potent generator of conformity.

Two things are growing among Nigerian adolescents in this century, affiliation with religious group as well as increase in premarital sexual intercourse. At every nook and cranny of Nigeria are religious houses with the majority of worshippers being youths. Premarital sexual intercourse among adolescents in Nigeria is also growing at an alarming rate despite its prohibition by these religious groups. Researchers are of the opinion that in spite of the apparent pervasive religiosity in the country, premarital sexual practices that culminate to unplanned pregnancy and sexually transmitted infections are on the increase (Dorojaiye, 2009; Morhason-Bello, Oladokun, Enakpene, Fabamiro, Obisesan and Ojengbede, 2008). A study argued that religion influence individual adolescents' sexual behaviour directly and indirectly through mechanisms of social support and social control interacting at multiple levels of the adolescents' social context (Durkheims, 1951). There is still controversy underlying the mechanism through which religion affects sexual behaviour of adolescents in Nigeria. Certainly, religious values are the source of moral proscriptions for many individuals the teachings of the churches and mosques are likely to play a role in the formation of individual attitudes, values and decisions. The extent to which specific doctrines and policies of the religion influences individual attitudes and behaviour is yet to be determined given Rohrbaugh and Jessor (1975) were of the opinion that religion generates social control through four pathways (a) by embedding the individual in an 'organised sanctioning network (p.137) that is supportive of conventional activities and opposed to unconventional ones, (b) by making the individual sensitive to moral issues and acceptable standards of behaviours, (c) by offering a deity as a source of punishment and wrath, and lastly by generating devoutness, thus creating an obedience orientation

Findings regarding influence of religion on sexual behaviours have been mixed. For example, a study by Odimegwu (2005) using 1,153 campus-based adolescents aged 10-24 years show a strong relationship between religiosity and adolescent sexual attitudes and behaviour. Similar finding was reported by Owusu (2011) using 1026 adolescents between 12 and 19 years of age in the result showed that religiosity is significantly related to multiple sexual partnerships. Crockett, Bingham, Chopak and Vicary (1996) found that females who attended religious services more frequently were more likely to delay sexual debut. Whereas, others (Mott, Fondell, Hu, Kowaleski-Jones and Menaghan, 1996) indicate that attendance was a predictor only when the adolescents' male friends also attended religious activities. Other studies reported non-significant findings for males (Miller, Norton, Curtis, Hill, Schvaneldt and Young, 1997).

Religiosity is expected to create religious values which forbid sexual relationship among the believers especially the young adolescents, religious belief frowns at the premarital sex and extra marital affairs, one began to wonder why despite the teachings on this among the religious followers, sexual risky behaviour are still on an increase. In view of the inconsistencies, this study, therefore, sought to investigate religiosity on risky sexual behaviour among the out of -school adolescents in Mushin, Lagos state, Nigeria.

Internet addiction is the last variable in this study. It is not news again that internet has become part and parcel of the individual lifestyle in the 21st century. The advancement of information and communication technology, with internet as one of its products, has brought great benefits to many individuals in the world. It allows easy communication and connection, sharing of information, some businesses to be carried out, or just to have fun/or entertain oneself.

The internet has made the life of many individuals easier and convenient. However, due to the availability of massive information, ability of individuals to store and retrieve whatever contents in line with their preference, and the availability of some unwanted elements, it is of disadvantage to some particular users, especially those that are not matured enough in terms of mental and intellect to process, select, and use the information wisely as well as those that are addicted to it. Internet Addiction (IA) can be defined as spending too much time on the Internet, accompanied by Psychological dependence on overuse of the Internet (Young and De Abreu 2010), IA is more prevalent among adolescents. The prevalence rates of internet addiction varied worldwide. In the USA, it ranged from 7.9 to 25.2% among adolescents while the East Asia and Africa had rates from 17.3 to 23.6%. A study in Asia showed that it varied among the adolescents, ranging from 8.1% to 50.9% (Xin , Xing, Pengfei, Houru, Mengcheng and Hong)

Studies have shown that IA could have a negative effect on the mental health status of adolescents and causes psychosocial stress, anxiety, depressive symptoms, sleep problems, alcohol abuse, attention deficit and hyperactivity and decreased self-esteem among them (Morrison and Gore (2010); Alam, Hazrul, Hashim, Ahmad, Aniza and Wel. (2014). Adolescents who use the Internet excessively are more likely to have a poorer health status, and engage in more risky behaviours such as smoking, alcohol use and drug use and risky sexual behaviours than others Guo, Luo, Wang, Huang, Gao, and Zhang (2018).

Adolescents who use the Internet excessively and engage in risky sexual behaviours may also receive or send sexual messages, which can lead to mental health problems, affect communicating with others and fall victim to sexual relations and engage in high-risk sexual behaviours (Merrill, 2018). Sexual curiosity among adolescents has led to exposure to pornography, indulgence in sexual activities, and also an increase in the vulnerability to sexual abuse (Kar, Choudhury and Singh 2015).

At present, the internet has advanced both socially and technologically, which influences the attitudes and perception of adolescents on sexuality which if not well managed could lead to higher sexual risky behaviour. A meta-analytic found that male adolescence in urban areas was 2.6 times likely to have higher risk sexual behaviour than those in suburban areas (Cooper, Delmonico and Burg 2000).

Given the popularity of the Internet amongst young persons, some researchers have investigated the relationship between young persons' involvement with online sexual activities (including online chats, meeting partners, and looking for romantic and sexual relationships) and the development of their sexuality. Cooper et al (2000) also found that excessive usage (as measured by time spent in viewing sexually related activities online) was positively related to stress and sexual sensation seeking. While much has been written on in- school adolescents on the internet usage, few studies have examined out- of school adolescents who have the tendency to engage in a higher level of risky sexual behaviour as a result of not being under the monitoring and control of the significant stakeholders like teachers, school management and to some extent their parents as some of these adolescents don't live with their parents again, this study therefore, aims to investigate the internet addiction and risky sexual behaviour among out- of school adolescents in Mushin, Lagos state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study;

1. What is the relationship that exists between religiosity, parental involvement, internet addiction and risky sexual behaviour among the participants?
2. What is the joint contribution of internet addiction, religiosity, parental involvement to risky sexual behaviour among the participants?
3. What is the relative contribution of each of internet addiction, religiosity, parental involvement to risky sexual behaviour among the participants?

Population of the Study

The population of this research work comprises of all the out- of school adolescents in Mushin, Lagos state. Mushin, town is located in Lagos state, Southwestern Nigeria. Mushin is a suburb of Lagos city, and its inhabitants are mostly Yoruba people. Mushin is the site of a large industrial estate. Commercial enterprises include spinning and weaving cotton, shoe manufacturing, bicycle and motorized-cycle assembly, and the production of powdered milk. Mushin lies on the railway from Lagos and at the intersection of roads from Lagos, Shomolu, and Ikeja. it is largely a congested

residential area with inadequate sanitation and low-quality housing. It had 633,009 inhabitants (NPC, 2006)

Sample and sampling technique

Multi stage sampling technique was used in selecting 272 out -of school adolescents from ten (10) different areas within Mushin, Lagos state., These include Oloosa, Iso pako Daleko and Ojuwoye Ilasamaja Oladipo Iidi oro Agoro Alasalat lawason Akala.

Instrumentation

Past and Present Sexual Behaviour Questionnaire developed by Snell (2001) was used to measure the risky sexual behaviour among the participants. They were required to report on several aspects of current and previous sexual relationships, such as length of and sexual exclusivity and number of previous sexual partners. It has ten (10) items. Two of the items are: “Have you ever engaged in unprotected vaginal sex”? “Did you use alcohol before engaging in sex?” The reliability coefficient after pilot-testing the scale for this study was 0.75.

Parental involvement was measured with three questions. The first question was ‘Do your parents know most of your friends?’ with response alternatives ‘they both know’ (coded for the analyses (=2), ‘only father knows’ (=1), ‘only mother knows’ (=1), and ‘neither of them knows’ (=0)). The second question was ‘Do your parents know about your whereabouts at nights?’ with response alternatives ‘always’ (=2), ‘sometimes’ (=1), and ‘mostly not’ (=0). The third question was ‘Are you able to talk with your parents about your sexual life?’ with response alternatives ‘often’ (=3), ‘fairly often’ (=2), ‘now and then’ (=1), and ‘hardly ever’ (=0). A sum score was formed of the responses so that the maximum score was 7. Scores 0–3 were referred to as low parental involvement, scores 4–5 to as average parental involvement, and scores 6–7 to as high parental involvement. The reliability coefficient after pilot-testing the scale for this study was 0.86. .

The Religiosity and Spirituality Scale for Youth by Hernandez, and Brittany (2011) was used to measure the participant’s sense of religiosity. The respondents were asked to pick only one option that best described their opinion on each item. It has thirty seven (37) items on the rating scale of four-point Likert Two of the Items on the scale include I have a close relationship with God; “my religious beliefs makes me happy”

Internet addiction scale by Young’s Internet Addiction Test (1998). (YIAT) was used to measure Internet addiction of the participants. It contains 20 self-report items. It classifies Internet addiction into mild, moderate, and severe degrees. The items are scored using a five-point Likert-type scale (1 = Rarely. 2 = Occasionally. 3 = Frequently. 4 = Often. 5 = Always). Scores between 20 and 49 denote normal Internet use, 50–79 represent moderate Internet use (moderate addiction), and 80–100 mean severe Internet use (severe addiction). It has Cronbach’s alpha of 0.90. The reliability of the scale was confirmed and it yielded a Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0.82

Research Question One. *Are there relationship between the independent variables (parental involvement, religiosity and internet addiction) and the dependent variable (risky sexual behaviour)?*

The result analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) is presented on the table below.

Models	Risky sexual behaviour	Parental involvement	Religiosity	Internet addiction
Risky sexual behaviour	1.00			
Parental involvement	-.293	1.00		
Religiosity	-.325	.032	1.00	
Internet addiction	-.258	.021	.018	1.00
N	272	272	272	272
Mean	35.99	55.14.	43.67	63.62
SD	10.48	13.38	13.08	10.11

Result of research question as presented on the table above indicate that risky sexual behaviours is negatively correlated with parental involvement (r=.293, p<0.05, religiosity (r=.325, P<0.05 and internet addiction (r=.258, p<0.05). This implies that the more the parents monitor and get involves in their children’s activities, the less likely, they will be involved in risky sexual practices. Also,

respondents who involve more in religious activities are also less likely to experiment with risky sexual behaviours. Finally, those that positively use the internet to their advantage will be less involve in risky sexual behaviours.

Research Question Two. *What is the joint contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable?*

Summary of Regression Analysis of the combined Prediction of Bullying among Participants by the Four Independent variables.

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
0.812	0.659	0.646	3.40304

SUMMARY REGRESSION ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P	Remark
Regression	3856.125	2	964.03	94.88	0.000	Sig
Residual	1991.875	269	10.16			
Total	5848.000	271				

From the results displayed on the table above, each of the independent variable made significant individual contributions to the prediction of the criterion measure (risky sexual behaviour) in varying weights. The results indicated that the following beta weights represent the predictive strength of the independent variables observed in accordance to the most effective to the least; religiosity ($\beta = .224$ $t = 2.318$, $P < 0.05$), internet addiction ($\beta = .231$ $t = 1.204$, $p < 0.05$) and parental involvement ($\beta = .201$, $t = 1.1272$, $P < 0.05$). It implies that while religiosity is the most potent factor in predicting risky sexual among out of -school adolescents, parental involvement was the least.

Research Question Three: *What is the relative contribution of each of the independent variable (parental involvement, religiosity and internet addiction) to the prediction of the dependent variable (risky sexual behaviour).*

Relative contribution of the Independent Variables to the Prediction risky sexual behaviour.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient	Standardized Coefficient	Standardized Coefficient	T	Sig.
	B	Std Error	Beta (β)		
Parental Involve.	1.203	.128	.201	1.172	001
Religiosity	1.082	.785	.224	2.318	003
Internet Addiction	1.105	.577	.231	1.204	.002

From the results displayed on the table above, each of the independent variable made significant individual contributions to the prediction of the criterion measure (risky sexual behaviour) in varying weights. The results indicated that the following beta weights represent the predictive strength of the independent variables observed in accordance to the most effective to the least; religiosity ($\beta = .224$ $t = 2.318$, $P < 0.05$), internet addiction ($\beta = .231$ $t = 1.204$, $p < 0.05$) and parental involvement ($\beta = .201$, $t = 1.1272$, $P < 0.05$). It implies that while religiosity is the most potent factor in predicting risky sexual among out of -school adolescents, parental involvement was the least.

DISCUSSION

This study examined the extent to which parental involvement, religiosity and internet addiction predicts risky sexual behaviour among out of -school adolescents in Mushin, Lagos state. Nigeria. The Correlation matrix presented in the table 1 indicated that there was a significant negative relationship between the independent variables (parental involvement, religiosity and internet addiction) and dependent variable (risky sexual behaviour).

Result of research question 2 as presented in table 2 above shows the magnitude of the prediction of the dependent variable by the independent variable as reflected in the values of coefficient of multiple R of 0.812 and a multiple R square of 0.646.. Thus, it can be concluded that . 64.6 % of the total variance in the risky sexual behaviours of the participants is accounted for by the combination of the four investigated independent. Consequently, the other 35.4% variation in sexual behaviours could be attributed to other factors not included in the present study. The F-ratio value of 94.88 was significant at 0.05 further affirms this position that the predictive capacity of the independent variables could not have been attributed to chance factor. This outcome is consistent with the findings in earlier qualitative studies where young people report that varieties of personal, familiar and social fathers and shaped their obedient in all spheres of life (Hamid Johansson and Rubenson, 2010).

The outcome suggests that when parents are more involved in their children's activities coupled with engagement of the adolescents in religiosity and positive internet activities risky sexual behaviours will be either be delayed or declined. This further gave credence to the theoretical proposition of Social ecology model/ecological-environmental health promotion model of Hawkins and Weiss (1985) and Kumpfer and Turner (1990) model of health promotion which viewed behaviour as being affected by, and affecting by systems. According to the theorists, the systems composed of five socially organized subsystems that influence, support and guide human behaviour. The subsystem includes: (1) intrapersonal or individual factors such as the individual level of self-efficacy; (2) interpersonal factors as in internet addiction; (3) institutional or organizational factors; (4) community factors as evident in religious and parental involvement; and (5) public policy and factors (McLeroy, Bibeau, Steck lerand Glanz, 1988).

With regard to the extent to which each of the three independent variables contributed to the prediction of risky sexual behaviours, as postulated in research question three it was observed that religiosity is the most potent predictor of risky sexual behaviour among the factors considered while parental involvement was the least. This further affirms the aphorism that religion is the opium of the society. This finding is supported by several empirical studies which demonstrate a negative association between level of religiosity and frequency of sexual risk-taking behaviours within emerging adulthood (Owusu, 2011; Odimegwu, 2005; Ofole and Agokei 2014) However, the nature of the influence of religious practices, beliefs on sexual control remains controversial. Some studies such as Carver and Scheier (1998), report that it is through self-control or self-regulation. Also, Odedokun (2022), claimed that religion has link with resilience among medical students

On the contrary, Smith (2003) reported that the link between religion and sexual behaviours is that the former influence the lives of the young "by increasing their competence in skills and knowledge that contribute to enhancing their well-being and improving their life chances". He structured such learned competences into these three factors namely: community and leadership skills, cultural capital, and coping skills. On the contrary, a recent study using in-school adolescents in Lagos, Nigeria report that religious affiliations enhances sexual activities of female respondents (Onipede, 2011). Parental involvement made the least contribution to prediction of sexual behaviours. This outcome is contrary to numerous research findings where parents improved involvement with their children activities was reported to reduce negative outcome of sexual experimentation (Buunk, Park and Duncan, 2009). On the contrary some researchers (Dishion and McMahon, 1998) are of the opinion that in later adolescents, parents are more likely to allow their teens the freedom to spend increased unsupervised time with peers as part of negotiated agreement between them and their adolescent. Additionally, parents may believe that they can monitor their teens if he/she entertains friends at home rather than at different location (i.e friends' house). They argued that such unsupervised freedom may lead to more opportunity for experimentation with sexuality and substances (Patterson, 1997; Patterson and StouthamerLeber, 1984).

Lastly, internet addiction significantly predicted risky sexual behaviour among the participants. Tis is in line with the work of Cooper

IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The result of this study reveals negative significant relationships between the variables investigated and risky sexual behaviours. The implication of this study is that these variables investigated could be protective and effective in reducing risky sexual behaviours among the participants. Moreover, programs designed to delay sexual activities may also benefit from including or enhancing parental

involvement in their offerings. Little by Little what they learn from the internet affects their lives either positively or negatively. Those that take advantage of the positive learning from internet never fall into risky behaviour of all sorts. But those that follow the negative learning are always in regret of the horrible outcome.

Parental involvement should also be component of sex education not merely as the usual ‘sex talk’ but a serious explorations of parenting practices since the study outcome suggests that several simple and affordable parental practices (involvement, monitoring, behaviour management) can help strengthen families and improve adolescent outcomes. Additionally, since identifying with a religion has been shown to have relationship with risky sexual behaviours adolescents should be encouraged to be affiliated to a religion group which eventually facilitates selection, pursuance and organization of goals.

CONCLUSION

The outcome of this study provided empirical evidence that out of school adolescents’ sexual behaviour is influenced by parental involvement, internet addiction religion Moreover, since religion directly and indirectly is reported to affect sexual decisions through religious norms and sanctions for noncompliance, the need to ensure that adolescents are affiliated to a religious group was suggested. Finally, the study has also confirmed that parental involvement in the lives of their children is linked with lower levels of sexual experimentation. It was recommended that any programme designed to delay sexual debut should include parental involvement component.

In addition, workshops and seminars should be organized to train parents on how to provide quality parenting and monitoring activities for their children vis a vis the usage of internet to avoid addiction which could promote risk sexual behaviour

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